

Some New β -Diketonates of Boron : Their Syntheses and Characterisation

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A number of substituted β -diketonates of boron having general formula

$$\text{OGOC(R)G : CON(R')N : CCH}_2 \quad (\text{where } \text{G}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3 \text{ and } -\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2; \text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}; \text{R}'=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$$

have been synthesised by the reactions of 4-acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (acyl=acetyl, propionyl, benzoyl and chloro-benzoyl) with 2-isopropoxy 4H-1, 3,2-benzodioxaborin, 2-isopropoxy 1,3,2-benzodioxaborole and 2-isopropoxy 5,5-dimethyl 1,1,3,2-dioxaborinane.

These derivatives have been characterised by elemental analyses and molecular weight determinations. The tetra coordination around boron atom in these complexes have been proposed on the basis of ir and pmr spectral evidences.

A survey of literature reveals that 4-acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (AcMPPOH) behave like β -diketones even in the presence of a heterocyclic ring system and 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (BMPPOH) has been widely used in solvent extraction of various transition¹⁻³ and rare earth metals⁴⁻⁶.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterisation of a number of boron complexes with the above class of ligands. Attempts have been made to establish their probable structure on the basis of ir and pmr spectral evidences.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Alkoxy/aryloxy boranes were prepared by literature⁷ method. The ligands were synthesised by the method reported by Jensen⁸ and were crystallised from *n*-heptane before use. Their purity was confirmed by m.p., tlc and spectral evidences. All the solvents were dried before use.

Synthesis of boron β -diketonates : The reactions of alkoxy/aryloxy boranes were carried out with 4-acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones in 1 : 1 molar ratio in refluxing benzene. Few representative reactions were also carried out in diethyl ether at room temperature. Since a similar pattern was followed in the synthesis of all the derivatives, the synthesis of only one derivative in both the media has been given in detail and the rests have been summarised in Table 1.

Reaction of 2-isopropoxy 1,3,2-benzodioxaborole with 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one in 1 : 1 molar ratio in benzene : A benzene solution of 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (2.47 g ; 1 mole) was mixed with the benzene

solution of 2-isopropoxy 1,3,2-benzodioxaborole (1.58 g ; 1 mole). The solution was refluxed over fractionating column. The isopropanol liberated during the course of the reaction was removed azeotropically with benzene. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the isopropanol in the azeotrope. After completion of the reaction, the excess solvent was distilled off and the compound was dried under reduced pressure. The compound was recrystallised from *n*-hexane-benzene mixture, yield 3.34 g (Calcd. 3.42 g) ; m.p. 267°. Found : B, 2.72 ; C, 69.47, H, 4.32. Calcd. B, 2.85 ; C, 69.69 ; H, 4.29 %.

Reaction of 2-isopropoxy 1,3,2-benzodioxaborole with 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ether : Interaction between 2-isopropoxy 1,3,2-benzodioxaborole (0.79 g ; 1 mole) and 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1.24 g ; 1 mole) resulted in simultaneous precipitation of a yellow product. The solid product was filtered, washed with ether and was dried under reduced pressure to yield a yellow coloured boron compound 1.61 g (Calcd. 1.76 g) having similar analysis as mentioned above.

Analytical methods and physical measurements : Boron was estimated as methyl borate⁹ and isopropanol was estimated by oxidation with $\text{N K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in 12.5 % H_2SO_4 ¹⁰. IR spectra were recorded as nujol mull by a 577-Perkin Elmer double grating spectrophotometer. PMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard by a Varian S-100 spectrophotometer. Carbon, hydrogen were analysed by Coleman-33 carbon hydrogen analyser. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically with Gallenkamp ebulliometer equipped with thermister sensor.

Results and Discussion

4-Acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA FOR SUBSTITUTED BORON β -DIKETONATES

Sl. No	Complexes*	Physical state	m p † °C	%B Found (Calcd.)	%C Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
1.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Yellow powder	176	3.20 (3.24)	64.90 (64.66)	4.58 (4.49)	342 (334)
2.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Pink powder	194	3.08 (3.10)	65.38 (65.51)	4.78 (4.86)	352 (348)
3.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Yellow powder	267	2.91 (2.85)	69.47 (69.69)	4.32 (4.29)	402 (396)
4.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}$	Light brown powder	202	2.58 (2.50)	—	—	—
5.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Orange red powder	146	3.02 (3.10)	65.81 (65.51)	4.80 (4.88)	361 (348)
6.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Light yellow powder	106	3.06 (3.10)	—	—	—
7.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Yellow powder	164	2.66 (2.68)	70.44 (70.24)	4.38 (4.63)	420 (410)
8.	$\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}$	Yellow powder	181	2.38 (2.42)	—	—	—
9.	$\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Brown viscous liquid	—	3.21 (3.29)	—	—	—
10.	$\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Brown viscous liquid	—	3.04 (3.14)	—	—	—
11.	$\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}$	Yellow solid	90	2.60 (2.66)	—	—	—
12.	$\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{OBO}_2\text{N}_2\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}$	Yellow powder	110	2.48 (2.54)	62.08 (62.19)	5.04 (5.18)	442 (424.5)

* $\text{C}_1\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ = 4-acetyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one.
 $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ = 4-propionyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one
 $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ = 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one.
 $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ = 4-chlorobenzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one.
 † All melting points are uncorrected and in the range of $\pm 1^\circ$.

(AcMPPOH) are known to exist in both keto and enol forms.

Keto Form

Enol Form

The existence of either of the two forms depends solely upon the nature of the solvents used for crystallisation⁶. The enolic form only interacts with alkoxy/aryloxy borane. Hence, all the ligands have been repeatedly crystallised from *n*-heptane solution to obtain the pure enolic form.

Since the reactions of 4-acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones with isopropyl borate were found to be very slow, mono-isopropoxy glycolate derivatives of boron were used for the synthesis of boron β -diketonates.

The reactions of OGOBOP^tr [where $\text{G} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2$ and $\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2$] were carried out with 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one [BMPPOH] in 1 : 1 molar ratio at room temperature in ether solution.

In the case where $\text{G} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, the reaction product separated out instantaneously on addition

TABLE 2—PMR SPECTRA DATA FOR SUBSTITUTED β -DIKETONES AND THEIR BORON DERIVATIVES IN δ WITH REFERENCE TO TMS

Sl. No.	Compound	Ring CH ₂ (ligand)	Phenyl protons (ligand)	Phenyl proton (Boron glycolate)	CH ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ or CH ₂ of ligand)	CH ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ of ligand)	CH ₂ O (Boron glycolate)
1.	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	2.40s	7.2-8.0m	—	2.60s	—	—
2.	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	2.44s	7.2-8.0m	—	1.15-1.3t	2.6-2.9q	—
3.	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	2.0s	7.1-7.9m	—	—	—	—
4.	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	1.95s	7.1-7.9m	—	—	—	—
5.	OC ₆ H ₄ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₂ H ₁₁	2.43s	7.21-7.86m	6.81s	2.58s	—	—
6.	O ₂ H ₄ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₂ H ₁₁	2.43s	7.21-7.86m	6.80s	1.2-1.60t	2.7-2.95q	—
7.	OC ₆ H ₄ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₇ H ₁₂	2.24s	7.21-7.86m	6.82s	—	—	—
8.	OC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₂ H ₁₁	2.10s	7.0-7.86m	6.7-7.0m	1.2-1.4t	2.7-2.95q	4.86s
9.	OC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₇ H ₁₂	2.20s	7.21-7.81m	6.81-7.0m	—	—	5.0s
10.	OC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₇ H ₁₂ Cl	2.10s	7.19-7.80m	6.70-7.8m	—	—	5.0s
11.	OCH ₂ C(CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ OBO ₂ N ₂ C ₁₇ H ₁₂	2.20s	7.21-7.80m	—	—	—	3.70s

* gem C(CH₃)₂ was observed at δ 0.90.
s=singlet, m=medium, t=triplet, q=quartet.

of the reactants whereas in the similar reaction where G=C₆H₄CH₂, the resulting product could be obtained only after about 8 hr of stirring. In the reaction where G=CH₂C(CH₃)₂CH₂, no product was isolated even after prolonged stirring at room temperature.

The reactions of OGOBOPr¹ [where G=C₆H₄ and C₆H₄CH₂ and CH₂C(CH₃)₂CH₂] were also carried out with 4-acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one in benzene solution. The isopropanol liberated in the reaction was fractionated off azeotropically with benzene and the progress of reaction was evaluated by estimating the amount of isopropanol in the azeotrope at different intervals.

The reactions where G=C₆H₄ and C₆H₄CH₂ were found to be quite facile, whereas the reactions where G=CH₂C(CH₃)₂CH₂ were found to be sluggish and could only be completed after a prolonged refluxing (~30 hr).

Attempt has also been made to study the reaction of 2-isopropoxy 4,4,6-trimethyl 1,1,3,2-dioxaborinone with BMPPOH in refluxing benzene. Although a small amount of isopropanol was detected in the azeotrope in about 30 hr of refluxing, the corresponding derivative could not be obtained.

These observations led us to conclude that

OC₆H₄OBOPr¹ (A) is more reactive as compared to OC₆H₄CH₂BOPr¹ (B) and OCH₂C(CH₃)₂CH₂OBOPr¹ (C). (A) is expected to exhibit a higher Lewis acidic character as compared to that of (C) because of the electron sink nature of catchol moiety in (A) which enhances its reactivity towards AcMPPOH. The presence of CH₂ group reduces the electron sink nature of catchol moiety to some extent and hence B is comparatively less reactive than (A).

All these derivatives have been obtained as coloured solids or viscous liquids, non-volatile in nature. They are soluble in benzene and chloroform but are insoluble or sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride and other common organic solvents. These derivatives are found to be monomeric in refluxing benzene.

Infrared spectra : A new medium intensity band appears at 710-730 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of all boron complexes and can be assigned to B←O¹¹. Another important stretching vibration observed at 1515-1490 cm⁻¹ in boron chelates has been assigned to ν C=O stretching frequency which appears in the spectra of ligands at 1540 $\pm$ 5 cm⁻¹. This shifting of 30-40 cm⁻¹ suggests that the coordination is through carbonyl oxygen. Some new bands appearing in the range of 1340-1260 cm⁻¹ have tentatively been assigned ν B-O¹². All other bands observed in the ligands spectra remained unaffected even after complexation.

PMR spectra : The pmr signals of the ligands and their boron complexes are given in Table 2. The pmr spectra of the ligands show a sharp singlet

at δ 12.1 due to $-\text{OH}$ protons. Moreover, there is no signal assignable to δ -CH protons. This confirms the existence of ligand in the enolic form only. A multiplet at δ 7.1-7.8 due to phenyl protons and a singlet at δ 2.1 due to CH_3 protons have also been observed in the spectra of all ligands. Some additional signals, a triplet, a quartet centered at δ 1.2 and δ 2.8 due to CH_3 and CH_2 groups (Ac=propionyl) and a sharp singlet at δ 2.4 (R=acetyl) due to CH_3 have also been observed. The singlet (δ 12.1), however, disappears from all the complexes of boron showing the deprotonation of $-\text{OH}$ proton during complex formation.

In the pmr spectra of the derivatives of the type $\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OBOC}(\text{R})\text{C}:\text{CON}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{N}:\text{CCH}_3$, a singlet at δ 6.8 due to C_6H_4 protons have been observed besides all the signals discussed above.

On the basis of the spectral evidences the following plausible structure has been proposed for the derivatives of the type $\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OBOPPMac}$.

[R=CH₃, C₂H₅, C₆H₅ and C₆H₄Cl]

In the spectra of the compounds like OGOBOPPMac [G=C₆H₄CH₂], a multiplet at δ 6.7-7.0 and a sharp singlet at δ 4.9 due to C_6H_4 and CH_2 protons, respectively, have also been observed in addition to ligand signals. In the spectrum of $\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{OBOPr}$, the methylene singlet is present at δ 5.03¹². This shift in its position appears to be influenced by the coordination number of boron which increases from three to four coordination state and therefore the following structure with tetra coordinate geometry of boron may be proposed.

[R=OH₂, C₂H₅, C₆H₅ and ClC₆H₄]

In addition to the above mentioned ligand signals in the pmr spectra, two sharp singlets at δ 0.9 and δ 3.6 have also been observed in the spectrum

of the derivative $\text{OCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{OBOPPMac}$ which may be assigned to gem-dimethyl and $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ protons, respectively. These complexes may have the following structures:

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